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Abstract

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project is a participatory and transdisciplinary initiative that aims to co-develop transformational pathways toward sustainable agrifood systems and trade. This report as Deliverable 2.3 of Work Package 2, adopts a consumer-centred approach to identify new pathways for change, presenting the results of surveys conducted with a total of 1,515 consumers in Sweden, the Netherlands, and Italy.

The findings indicate that consumers make only moderate use of sustainability labels—currently one of the most discussed instruments for promoting sustainable consumption—and that they perceive little potential for progress through shaming campaigns, another common strategy. Nonetheless, there is a broad consensus among respondents that transformative change is needed.

Consumers identified several key instruments to drive such change, including price adjustments, lowering the prices of sustainable products and increasing those of unsustainable ones; clear sustainability rankings, preferably displayed in stores rather than via apps or websites; and loyalty incentives for purchasing sustainable products.

Together, these findings suggest that the most promising pathway for change lies in modifying the store environment. Logical next steps include initiating a public debate on the role of retailers in enabling responsible consumption, organizing roundtable discussions with retailers and value chain actors, and exploring legislative measures to support such transformations.

The results also point to a need to shift the research agenda, placing greater emphasis on price-based instruments, effective communication of sustainability rankings, and consumer incentives such as loyalty programs, in addition to the continued study of sustainability labels.

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1. Introduction

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project is a participatory, transdisciplinary initiative that seeks to co-develop transformational pathways toward sustainable and biodiversity-friendly agrifood systems and trade. The project responds to the urgent global need to reduce biodiversity loss driven by agricultural commodity production and international trade.

Demand from the European Union (EU) agrifood systems is a significant driver of land-use change in biodiversity-rich regions of the Global South. This contributes to deforestation, ecosystem degradation, and species decline. Addressing the EU's global biodiversity footprint is therefore a key priority in EU policy frameworks, including the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and the European Green Deal. While scientific evidence emphasizes the need for transformative change in economic, social, and financial systems, there remains limited practical knowledge on how such transformations can be achieved—particularly in ways that address trade-offs and synergies between biodiversity, climate resilience, and equity.

TCforBE aims to bridge this gap by co-generating applied knowledge, tools, and stakeholder capacities to support safe and just transitions in telecoupled agrifood systems—that is, systems linked across long distances through trade and value chains. The project brings together diverse stakeholders from the EU and three partner countries: Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya, including:

A consumer-country perspective

This deliverable (D2.3) adopts a consumer-centered perspective rather than a production-oriented one. Instead of viewing telecoupled value chains as linear systems that begin with production and end with consumer markets, we start with the consumer and its surrounding retailing and policy environment as the driving force of change. Consumer needs, preferences, values, and purchasing power shape demand, which in turn influences supply dynamics on the production side of the value chain.

We approach consumers, embedded in consumption stimulating environments, at a theoretical level of abstraction, thus focusing on the essential issues of the role of consumers in telecoupled food value chains and making our study less prone to rapid changing consumer tastes. Such more concrete information is included in deliverable 2.1. This perspective also guides how we define sustainability issues. From a consumer perspective, sustainability challenges—can be positioned along a continuum from issues with direct, immediate impact on “me now” to those affecting “others later” through long-term or distant consequences (Ingenbleek et al., 2015). Rather than limiting our analysis to issues that are central to the production-side of the TCforBE project, such as biodiversity loss and equity, we consider a broader scope. Accordingly, our analysis is not restricted to the cocoa and coffee value chains examined by the production-focused components of TCforBE. We may also draw on additional value chains and sustainability issues when relevant to understanding consumer behavior and decision-making. Ultimately, however, the goal remains aligned with the broader project mission: to identify transformative pathways that help address biodiversity and equity challenges in the project's focal value chains.

Objectives

This report presents the results of Task 2.3, which investigates how interventions, such as product labels, corporate brands, marketing strategies, and benchmarking systems influence consumer decision-making and how they can be leveraged to support biodiversity and equity outcomes in agrofood systems. The findings contribute to the development of **transformative change pathways** that can shift consumer behaviour toward more sustainable choices. The task has three main objectives:

1) Analyse the current landscape of sustainability instruments in the market

Conduct a state-of-the-art review and mapping of a selected set of product labels, corporate brands, and benchmarking systems to understand how they influence consumers with selected European countries. The analysis includes among others a conceptualization of policy options to influence sustainable purchasing behavior of consumers in telecoupled value chains.

2) Assess consumer perceptions and decision-making across Europe

Carry out consumer surveys in three European countries (Sweden, the Netherlands, and Italy) to:

1. Evaluate consumer satisfaction with existing labelling, branding, and benchmarking systems in relation to biodiversity and other sustainability dimensions, including levels of trust, awareness, cultural relevance, and perceived agency.
2. Examine the preferences of consumers for different policy options to strengthen sustainability behaviour (e.g. in-store promotions, online retail cues, mobile applications, price interventions, and product information tools).
3. Explore consumer responses to hypothetical new system innovations with improved biodiversity performance to identify potential opportunities for innovation.

3) Co-develop and test transformative change pathways for consumer behaviour

Identify and co-design leverage points that can enable more sustainable consumer choices in selected EU countries. This includes strategies to reduce barriers in consumer environments—for example, by making biodiversity benchmark data accessible through digital tools that provide personalised feedback on biodiversity and equity impacts. The two most promising innovations are tested through consumer experiments. The development of this deliverable was informed by extensive stakeholder engagement, including participation in policy workshops and conferences, as well as direct interactions with several key stakeholders.

2. Background

Current patterns of food consumption place considerable pressure on global food production systems, where commodities, products, and goods are exchanged through telecoupled value chains (Li et al., 2013; Eakin et al., 2013). Telecoupled value chains are defined as interconnected production, distribution, and consumption systems that are physically distant from one another (Liu et al., 2013). Within these systems, prevailing consumption practices have diverse negative impacts, including threats to biodiversity (Ambikapathi et al., 2022; Willett et al., 2019) and the perpetuation of social inequalities (Lawrence et al., 2019; McDermott et al., 2023). For example, countries consuming global commodities such as coffee, cocoa, and palm oil have effectively outsourced their biodiversity footprint to producing countries, resulting in deforestation and the loss of ecosystem services (Willett et al., 2019; Ambikapathi et al., 2022).

Telecoupled value chains are also characterised by unequal profit distribution, as farmers in many producing countries often receive only a minimal share of the value they create due to market volatility, exploitative pricing structures, and power asymmetries with dominant multinational corporations (Lawrence et al., 2019; McDermott et al., 2023). Furthermore, commodity production has been associated with child labour, gender inequalities, and the marginalisation of local communities in decision-making processes (Alho et al., 2021; Garrett et al., 2021), reinforcing historical colonial trading legacies of the global North (Bhambra, 2020).

Given these socio-environmental externalities, many scholars have called for transformative change in food systems to simultaneously conserve biodiversity and promote social equity. Yet, addressing local agricultural policies in producing countries alone is insufficient if the demand for cheap commodities

continues to drive exploitation (Rueda & Lambin, 2013; Clark & Tilman, 2017; Eakin et al., 2017; Ingram et al., 2020). Producer-side policies and initiatives are important, but they must be complemented by strategies that consider demand and consumer behaviour to foster transformative change across telecoupled value chains (Leeuwis et al., 2021).

In consumer regions such as the European Union (EU), a range of initiatives and mechanisms aim to promote sustainable telecoupled value chains. Public-sector efforts include multilateral and international collaborations that support mechanisation, conservation, and development programs in producing regions (Rueda & Lambin, 2013). The private sector and non-governmental organisations have implemented Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSS)—non-state initiatives that promote environmental, social, and economic sustainability. VSS include certifications, labels, round tables, and working groups adopted voluntarily by companies, civil society, and sometimes governments (Lambin et al., 2018; Bager & Lambin, 2022; Cramm et al., 2024). Marketing strategies also aim to influence consumer behaviour through pricing, product information, and other choice architecture mechanisms (Rothschild, 1999). Additionally, NGOs and social movements promote local and agroecological food systems to encourage the consumption of sustainable, healthy products in Europe or to foster sustainable and equitable production practices in producing countries (Dentoni et al., 2017).

Despite these initiatives, the market share of sustainable products in the EU remains limited, and sustainability concerns have only partially influenced consumer behaviour (Willett et al., 2019; BEUC, 2020; FiBL & IFOAM, 2022). Interventions have struggled to address the complexity of telecoupled value chains, including multi-level governance structures and the range of stakeholders involved (Rockström et al., 2016; Díaz et al., 2019; Willett et al., 2019).

To address these challenges, EU policies under the Green Deal emphasise changes in value chains to increase sustainability (Willer et al., 2022). For example, the EU Deforestation-Free Regulation (EU 2023/1115) aims to reduce imports of commodities linked to deforestation, including coffee, cocoa, and palm oil (European Commission, 2020; European Commission, 2023). Moreover, digital and data-driven technologies—such as blockchain and mobile applications—are being deployed to enhance value chain traceability and monitoring.

While these consumer-side strategies are important, they are insufficient on their own to achieve systemic transformative change, as they are often developed in isolation across different disciplines, stakeholders, and institutions, including marketing, food systems, and governance (O'Rourke & Lollo, 2015; Béné, 2022). Consequently, producer-side interventions will remain limited in effectiveness as long as the demand for socially and environmentally harmful products persists (Weinzettel et al., 2013), indicating the significant dependency of the producing and consumption system (Liu et al., 2013).

3. Transformative change pathways in consumer countries

Köhler et al. (2019, p. 2) provide a comprehensive summary of the emerging literature on sustainability transitions, motivated by the recognition that many environmental challenges—such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and resource depletion (e.g., clean water, oil, forests, and fish stocks)—constitute grand societal challenges. These challenges arise from unsustainable production and consumption patterns within socio-technical systems, including electricity, heat, buildings, mobility, and agro-food systems. According to Köhler et al. (2019), these problems cannot be addressed through incremental improvements or technological fixes alone but require radical shifts toward new socio-technical systems, which are referred to as sustainability transitions.

Sustainability transitions, as conceptualised in the literature, exhibit several distinctive characteristics (Köhler et al., 2019). First, they are multi-dimensional and co-evolving, encompassing technologies, markets, user practices, policies, supply chains, and distribution channels. Each dimension may follow its own trajectory, and co-evolution across dimensions can be uneven, potentially resulting in

conflicting or uncoordinated changes. Second, transitions are multi-actor processes, involving diverse actors—including market participants, civil society, policymakers, and academic institutions—who exercise distributed agency. These processes often involve sense-making, strategic decision-making, learning, investment, and negotiation, and can include conflicts between competing interests. Third, transitions combine stability and change: even as innovative “green” solutions emerge, existing systems may remain deeply entrenched or “locked in,” making change difficult. Fourth, transitions are long-term processes, as unlocking complex systems requires time and patience. Fifth, transitions are open-ended and uncertain, encompassing multiple innovations, initiatives, and potential pathways, with uncertain outcomes. Sixth, transitions are value-dependent and contested, reflecting disagreement among actors about priorities and pathways; for instance, radical proposals from special-interest groups may clash with the interests of established industries. Finally, transitions exhibit normative directionality, as sustainability is a public good and prone to commons dilemmas. Societal guidance, including public policy or advocacy by interest groups, is required to orient transformative efforts.

The concept of food systems transformation towards sustainability has been applied to capture varying conceptions of change, from adaptive and reform-oriented strategies to radical, regime-shifting transformations (Juri et al., 2024). Different paradigms of change are linked to how problems are defined in the literature. For example, when challenges are framed as technological, solutions often emphasise rapid, technology-driven innovations, such as artificial intelligence adoption.

Transformation entails profound, structural changes that can reshape entire sectors—such as energy, food, and urban systems—while also altering social, economic, and political structures, including values and institutions (Blythe et al., 2018; Moore et al., 2014; Termeer et al., 2024). Unlike adaptation or resilience, transformation represents a radical reordering of existing systems, although questions remain regarding the critical elements of transformation, how academic concepts translate into practice, and the broader social, political, and environmental implications (Burch et al., 2014; Blythe et al., 2018).

The literature distinguishes multiple approaches to transformative change. Following Scoones et al. (2020), three complementary perspectives can be identified. Structural approaches focus on fundamental changes in governance and societal practices of production and consumption (Clark & Tilman, 2017; Van Bers et al., 2019; Eakin et al., 2023; Juri et al., 2024). Systemic approaches emphasise steering complex systems by addressing interdependencies among institutions, technologies, and actors (Geels, 2002; Geels & Schot, 2007). Emancipatory approaches highlight human agency, values, and capacities to navigate uncertainty and actively shape desired futures (Chan et al., 2020; Scoones et al., 2020).

These three approaches are mutually complementary and are synthesised in the IPBES (2019) definition of transformative change as “a fundamental system-wide reorganisation across technological, economic, and social factors, including paradigms, goals and values, needed for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, good quality of life and sustainable development.” Transformative change of telecoupled food systems should go beyond behavioural shifts or technological scaling and it requires a fundamental shift in meaning-making, moving away from exploitative or controlling systems towards food systems that could be grounded in interdependence and stewardship, and where biodiversity conservation and social equity could drive the markets at the side of core economic transactions (O’Brien, 2021)..

4. State of the art mapping

In [TC4BE Deliverable D2.1](#) on international biodiversity governance initiatives, we presented an initial mapping, review of evidence, and case studies of international biodiversity governance initiatives, and

co-generated transformative change pathways to inform EU policymakers, consumers, citizens, and business. Continuing this work, we collected additional information using desk research and expert and stakeholder interviews on product labels, corporate brands, and benchmarks, including their strategies of influence and governance arrangements (including aspects like claims, assurance processes, market share, equity, producer incomes). Table 4.1 shows the additional interviews and other important pieces of evidence that we have collected for the current deliverable in addition to those already collected for D2.1.

Table 4.1 Overview of additional data collected for mapping exercise in D2.3

Type of stakeholder	Data collection source (interview, meeting attendance, document analysis, serious games)	Additional information
Conference, workshop and webinar attendance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chocoo 2024. 5-8 February 2024. Amsterdam, The Netherlands. • Amsterdam Coffee Event • London Cocoa Academy 2024 • European Cocoa Academy Meeting 2025 • Chocoo 2025 • Workshop EUDR. WWF Belgium, November 2024/February 2025 • Webinar provided by Fairtrade, WWF. • EUDR workshop provided by Preferred by Nature NL. 6/11/2025 • Presentations of consultancy reports to Max Kofi (on Fairtrade coffee chain innovations) 2024 • Guest lecture and workshop by head sustainability and regenerative agriculture. Unilever (2024) • Guest lecture and discussion meeting with Rewe (2025) 	Presence at important events related to the consumer-countryside of focal telecoupled value chains (cocoa and coffee). Ideas were exchanged with other participants; directions searched for document analyses, and contacts made for subsequent in-depth interviews.
In-depth interviews	Interviews with representants of Private, public, and societal sectors working in the European Union and West Africa.	Interviews discussed the background and point of views of the actors, as well as transition options and directions (depending on the actor, the specific topics varied)
Other meetings	Serious games played in Chocoo, 2024, with representatives from NGOs, private sector, public sector, social movements, consumers (EU), and producers (Cameroon).	Serious games are games designed for educational, training, or problem-solving objectives. They leverage the engaging elements of gaming—rules, challenges, rewards, interaction—to facilitate learning, or exploration of complex systems.

We used an iterative process to develop a final state-of-the-art mapping of transitional market-based policy instruments. We departed from D2.1 and reflected on this information from several lines of relevant literature (including, among others, work on food system transitions, general literature on transition processes, sustainable marketing and consumer behaviour, and consumer policy). We also reflected on our ideas in conversations with stakeholders and experts and presented our work in seminars. This led to further data collection, consultation of additional literature, adjustments to initial mapping, and so on. The process ended when we felt that our “map”, a categorisation of the relevant transformative policy instruments as a basis for developing transformative pathways, had reached theoretical saturation. This meant that it included all the important categories of instruments that we had come across. The categories can also be placed along a conceptual dimension that is relevant from a consumer perspective. We draw in this respect on freedom of choice theories (something we will present in the chapter on co-development of transformative change pathways). Below, we will present the categories from our mapping in a logical order, where helpful, explained with examples obtained during our iterative research process. As we will not reference all consulted articles and reports, a list of consulted sources can be found in Annex 1.

1. *Education campaigns* refer, according to a definition from social marketing to the design, implementation, and control of programs calculated to influence the acceptability of social ideas and involving considerations of product planning, pricing, communication, distribution, and marketing research (Kotler and Zaltman 1971). This group of interventions draws on basic economic assumptions that consumers are rational and fully informed. A sustainable choice is for consumers; thus, the rational choice given that, in the long term, they will experience negative consequences from unsustainable choices. However, in practice, many consumers do not choose sustainably. The reasoning suggests that a market failure may occur, which is usually caused by information asymmetry. In other words: If consumers do not make rational and sustainable choices, it is probably because they lack information. Education campaigns, sharing information on unsustainable consumer behaviours and choices, can be seen as the most basic instrument to share such information. Others have also suggested that consumer campaigns are important additions to other instruments, like sustainability labels, because consumers need an explanation of the meaning of such labels to use them effectively.

2. *Transparency requirements* are initiatives that encourage or enforce companies to disclose the relevant sustainability information. Following the reason underlying the consumer campaigns, consumers can only make a rational choice if they are fully informed. When it comes to sustainability aspects, these are often attributes that pertain to the production side of the chain. Especially when chains are long, such information may be lost. A coffee roaster from Europe who first visited coffee farmers in Latin America was, for example, shocked when he saw the living standards of coffee farmers. He would become the first coffee roaster to produce Fairtrade coffee for the supermarket channel. Transparency is also a clear advantage of short supply chains, as any chain that makes a close connection between production and consumption. Some companies sign up for certification programs, like B-Corp, that require them to collect and disclose sustainability information on a wide range of topics. European Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) legislation forces companies to disclose such information. In general, in several meetings, participants hinted to us on the fact that feedback from natural resources that ultimately produce our food to buyers in the chain or consumers is distorted (as it only comes in the form of price increases when supplying regions dry up or misharvest) or are even mostly absent. Connecting decisions, like purchase orders, directly to the (expected) impact on natural resources would further increase the transparency of the food system. Possibly, digital innovation can help establish this further (see also chapter 6 for more ideas on feedback mechanisms).

3. *Shaming*, consists of two processes in which *naming* refers to the process where companies or their stakeholders strengthen the reputation of their company name or its brand(s) because of their achievements in the sustainability domain, and shaming refers to the process in which stakeholders publicly expose companies for being detrimental to sustainability or for claiming positive contributions to sustainability that are not true. The latter is sometimes also called Green washing. Central to these processes is that companies and/or their stakeholders involve consumers in the stakeholder debate about what is sustainable and not and what is expected from companies when it comes to sustainability. The involvement of consumers is a logical step because positive reputations towards consumers are worth a lot. Consumers use brands as signals for reliability and cues for product selection, especially in categories like food, where the decision-making process is often cognitively low. A big international brand name like Nestlé is, for example, worth billions of dollars. Likewise, a shaming campaign against such a brand can significantly decrease the value of a brand, and with that of the company. For the company that owns such a brand, strengthening the sustainability in the supply chains can therefore be a rational action, even when it has no plans to communicate its sustainability program to consumers. Preventing others do so may be reason enough. Nevertheless, the risk of being shamed is not a guarantee for a strong sustainability program: Unilever, a company with particularly strong brands and until recently a forerunner in sustainability, decided to abandon its road towards becoming a net positive company in 2025.

4. *Persuasive cues* are signs that appear at the point of purchase, usually the moment in which the consumer is in the offline or online store, making a pick from the assortment, to persuade the consumer to go for the sustainable alternative. Cues are any stimulus or signal that triggers a response, perception, or decision in a consumer (e.g., Anderson and Simester 2008). A cue can therefore be a visual highlight like an arrow pointing at an Organic product with the text “find your Organic product here”, but more likely it’s a sustainability label. Sustainability labels are marks that communicate that a product or service complies with defined environmental, social, or ethical standards, usually consisting of a name and logo (cf. Thøgersen & Nielsen 2016). They are probably by far the most well-known, well-studied and often used instruments trying to make consumer behaviour more sustainable. Note that from the production perspective, the label is an end-of-pipeline instrument that is necessary to communicate the fact that the product is produced against certain standards with which producers and/or other actors in the chain comply. This is, of course, essential: without compliance no sustainability impact. In that respect, companies can also choose for the certification but not for a label. Think, for example, of Global GAP standards, which are usually not explicitly communicated to consumers. From the perspective of the consumer, that label is, however, the thing that often makes the difference between a sustainable purchase (thereby giving support to the entire certification effort) or not. It is therefore essential that consumers recognise the label, know what it stands for and trust that the certification is genuine. These are all aspects that can be questioned as consumers make decisions for fast-moving consumer goods in a split second when they act in an environment with literally tens of thousands of products that all want their attention. Education campaigns are, for that reason, suggested as a complementary instrument to explain the meaning of the labels. But being highlighted also makes them vulnerable to a negative press when something appears to be wrong in the certification process, and things certainly may go wrong, especially when production takes place in institutionally more vulnerable environments of developing and emerging economies. Digitalisation of the certification process, for example, with blockchain data, has been suggested as a means to strengthen the certification and make the labels more transparent for consumers.

5. *Pre-selecting sustainability preferences* refers to a process in which consumers use tools, like apps on their mobile phone, to get more control over the selection of their so-called consideration set, which is the set of products that a consumer considers when shopping for a particular product. In the past, some researchers have pointed at the slightly schizophrenic attitude of consumers towards sustainable products. In questionnaires, they often indicate having a positive attitude towards such products, but in shopping practice, they still tend to select cheaper, non-sustainable products. The shopping environment is at least partly due to the difference, because of the overwhelming number of cues that consumers receive, they tend to routinely select the options that are cheaper, discounted or simply more on display. That is, if these products are in the consideration set of consumers. With the digitalisation of the shopping environment, new opportunities emerge to develop new tools or apps that give consumers more control over their selection process. An app could, for example, ask them at a quiet moment back home about their sustainability preferences and then use these settings to select the products that fall within their range. In a digital environment, the app could filter out the products that fall within the acceptable set for a consumer by interfering in the shopping environment. Alternatively, AI tools may be developed that offer different alternatives for the consumer generated from different online shops, to do then make the actual purchases for the consumer on the online stores (protecting the consumer from the store environment). In an offline store, the digitalisation of the process is more difficult, but we did come across of startups that develop such selection tools in which consumer can scan the shelves through the screen of their phone, with the app then filtering the products that are not within their range. The use of Google glasses and the like would make such a process even easier.

6. *Nudging* refers to a subtle change in the way choices are presented that alters people's behaviour in a predictable way without restricting options or significantly changing economic incentives (Thaler & Sunstein, 2008). In other words, nudging makes use of the psychological aspects of decision-making about which consumers are less aware when making such decisions. Examples include placing products on eye-level in the shelves of the supermarket, presenting them as a barrier shelf that one needs to walk around to reach the cashier, attractively presented products that catch attention at the payment desk, or making the sustainable option the default option in an online shopping space. While in the past such marketing tricks were often used to sell unhealthy and unsustainable products, increasingly stores use these techniques to sell consumers more sustainable and healthier foods.

7. *Non-financial incentives* are non-monetary presents or gifts provided to consumers, think of extra points on your loyalty card when making sustainable purchases, free products for consumers with a sustainable shopping basket, or even loyalty point penalties when buying unsustainable products. Incentives are a classic instrument to steer behaviour and many store chains have an infrastructure of providing incentives readily available. Though not debated heavily (yet), some authors suggested deploying these to stimulate sustainable consumer decisions.

8. *Price (dis-) incentives*, are the monetary counterpart of the non-financial incentives. Price incentives intend to establish a price difference between sustainable and non-sustainable products in the advantage of the sustainable products. Often, sustainable products experience a price disadvantage for the simple reason that they try to prevent the overuse of natural and social resources. The resulting price premium for sustainable products is often brought up as a major reason for the relatively small market shares of sustainable products. Initiatives like True pricing, which calculate all the environmental costs involved with consuming certain products, even claim that the price differences are in fact even bigger than they appear now in the store. The solution that is suggested is to increase

the prices of unsustainable products, think, for example, of a fat tax, and reward sustainable purchasing by subsidising sustainable products. A simple example of this principle is charging extra for plastic bottles at the counter, and giving that money to the person who brings back the empty bottle to the store.

9. *Choice editing/assortment restriction* refers to cutting out unsustainable products and getting real sustainable choices on the shelves (SDC 2006). While the SDC sees price interventions as one way of choice editing, we restrict ourselves to assortment interventions: If the unsustainable products aren't there, consumers can't buy them. This intervention is different from the pre-selection that was mentioned earlier, where consumers themselves set the criteria. In this option, they are simply confronted with a smaller assortment. Some stores experimented with this on a small scale, for example, by offering only sustainable options for items that are small in turnover. Consider a supermarket that mostly sells cut, ready-to-use onions and where the sales of uncut onions as a consequence, are declining. By offering only sustainable uncut onions, the supermarket acts more sustainably but also saves valuable shelf space and replenishment costs. A more drastic example is the Organic store, where the entire supermarket is, in fact, offering Organic products. For the consumer, this eases the decision-making because the only decision made about the desired sustainability level is the decision in which store to shop. Subsequently, we heard the suggestion that perhaps all supermarkets need a label indicating the sustainability range of products that they offer (with the Organic store logically being at the upper end) and requiring them to stick to this level, thus constraining their assortment one sustainability level.

10. *Licensing* means that buyers need a license to be able to purchase unsustainable products. As such, the unsustainable products aren't banned, but they become only accessible to those people who need them. For example, a membership card of a food bank will allow you to pick the unsustainable, cheaper options from the shelves, because you are less likely to be able to afford a shopping cart filled with expensive sustainable products. Another option is to set a quota: while the membership of a food bank allows you to buy unsustainable products for 250 euros a month, a social welfare benefit without a food bank membership gives you access to only 100 euros of unsustainable shopping a month. When you're in the highest income tax class, you are expected to do all shopping sustainably.

11. *Legislative ban on unsustainable products* simply means that unsustainable products are no longer available because they are legally banned.

Below we present the results from our mapping exercise in Table 4.2. Interestingly, all the categories that we presented above take some position the dilemma between choice freedom for consumers on the one hand and sustainability on the other. A legislative ban on all unsustainable products is for example likely to be highly effective in improving sustainability, but it goes clearly at the expense of the choice freedom of consumers. On the other hand, if consumers are confronted with a large assortment of different options, including very cheap ones that have detrimental effects on sustainability, and consumers receive some information about these detrimental effects and the importance of their choice through a campaign, choice freedom is clearly high, but the positive effect of the intervention campaign on sustainability can be questioned. Hence, the freedom of choice perspective is a central dimension in our map, and the proposed interventions can accordingly be grouped in four underlying mechanisms, namely

- *informing*, which assumes that consumers can, in principle, be trusted in making sustainable choices as long as they are sufficiently aware,
- *aiding*, which assumes that informing alone is not enough because consumers may lack the ability to make sustainable choices in the complex shopping environment that they are confronted with,
- *steering*, which assumes that helping consumers isn't enough, they should be actively steered to make sustainable choices, and
- *restricting*, which assumes that sustainability is fact, unlikely to be achieved unless consumers are in some way constrained in their choices.

Table 4.2: Conceptualization of the levels of choice freedom in sustainable consumer decision-making

Level	Intervention	Nickname	Description	Examples
Informing	1. Education campaigns	Education campaigns	More information for consumers about the sustainability impacts of specific products through public awareness campaigns.	Government campaigns drawing attention to specific considerations, like to buy more fruits and vegetables, or more local products.
	2. Transparency requirements	Sustainability rankings	Put more pressure on companies to disclose objective detailed sustainability information to consumers. This information can for example be used to rank companies from most to least sustainable in food categories.	Benchmark websites that compare retailers and brands on sustainability criteria (e.g., Corporate Human Rights Benchmark, KnowTheChain, carbon Disclosure Project).
	3. Naming and Shaming	Shaming	More “shaming” campaigns that tell consumers which brands and companies are not sustainable, so that consumers may get disappointed in these brands and companies.	Sustainable brands include among others Ben & Jerry’s, the Vegetarian Butcher and the Bodyshop. Shaming campaigns include among others Greenpeace’s Detox my fashion, Oxfam’s Behind the Brands, and the Clean Clothes campaign.
Aiding	4. Persuasive cues	Sustainability labels and reminders	Use more visual signals in the store, such as sustainability labels and highlights, to remind consumers which products are sustainable.	In supermarkets, a certain percentage of promotions has to be on sustainable products, which are highlighted and promoted through social norms messaging, visual signals, and positive messaging highlighting good product characteristics.
	5. Pre-Selecting Sustainability Preferences	Pre-selecting products	Develop more apps and other tools that help consumers to pre-select products that they find sufficiently sustainable, so that they get less distracted by the unsustainable products in the store.	Customers of supermarkets can input their shopping list and their preferred level of sustainability into an AI tool. This tool selects what groceries correspond with their preferred level of sustainability and are available in store.
Steering	6. Nudging	Unintended purchases	Make stores position more sustainable products in prominent areas within the store, such as at eye level, to increase the chance that consumers unintentionally chose these products.	Placing products in the most prominent locations, such as shelf ends and at the check-out counters to bring these products to the consumers’ attention giving them an advantage over other (non-sustainable) products and encouraging impulse buying.
	7. Non-financial incentives	Loyalty points	Make stores offer considerably more loyalty points with the purchase of sustainable products	Supermarkets provide sustainability incentives through their loyalty cards through which consumers can save for discounts or gifts..

			and considerably less with unsustainable products.	
	8. Price incentives	(dis-) Price decreases and increases	Use tax instruments to make sustainable products cheaper at the expense of unsustainable products that become more expensive.	Organic products on discount, fat tax, CO2 charges, loyalty card points for buying sustainable products, True Pricing Initiative.
Restricting	9. Choice editing/assortment restriction. Decrease the variation in sustainability-levels inside the store	Every store one sustainability level	Decrease the variation between very sustainable and unsustainable products in a store so that consumers choose their preferred sustainability level when they decide which store they go. In the store the products differ less in sustainability than they do now.	All products in a supermarket have to abide to certain sustainability requirements, like in an Organic store all products are Organic.
	10. Licensing	Licensing	Introduce more barriers for purchasing unsustainable products, so that only users that really need these products, like for example food banks, can purchase them.	In supermarkets, you can only purchase unsustainable products if you have signed up using your customer card prior to your visit. Sustainable products are available to everyone, like you can only buy alcohol when showing an 18+ ID card.
	11. Legislative ban on unsustainable products	Legislative ban on unsustainable products	Remove more unsustainable products entirely from all stores by legislation.	Governments no longer allowing specific unsustainable products, like asbestos, or private sector agreements to remove certain products from all stores, like cage eggs.

5. Consumer surveys in three EU countries

Research methods

We conducted surveys among 1500 consumers, divided over three EU countries, namely the Netherlands (n=500), Sweden (n=500), and Italy (n=500). The countries were selected because change and innovation are known to spread in a 'waterfall' from north to south; hence, to cover the geographical and cultural differences, the three European countries were selected. Data were collected by professional market research companies in the three countries. Questions pertained among others to consumer efficacy (ability to express your own needs for sustainability in your environment), satisfaction with sustainability labels, awareness of sustainability labels, benchmarks, and information behind brands, trust in sustainability of brands, trust in labels, and legitimacy (fit with cultural norms).

For this project, a quantitative, online survey was used to collect the data. Selected panel members were invited by e-mail to participate in the survey. Clicking on a hyperlink in the invitation, unique for each respondent, redirected them to the survey. The survey was only accessible for panel members who received an invitation to participate.

The target group of the survey consisted of 500 Dutch, 500 Italian and 500 Swedish inhabitants aged 18- 64 years old who are responsible for the groceries at home. To determine the research sample, respondents were selected from ISO-certified panels of the research companies. Because the exact characteristics of the target group are unknown (18-64 years old who are responsible for the groceries at home), the sample was stratified on the general population aged 18 to 64 years old. To determine who is responsible for the groceries at home, a selection question was asked at the beginning of the questionnaire. Stratified sampling was applied on the Dutch respondents for the following background characteristics: gender, age, region and educational level. This means that the respondents in the sample were aimed to be representative of the Dutch population, aged 18-65, regarding these characteristics. The background characteristics are known for all panel members and were updated at least once in the past year. The market research companies in Sweden and Italy sent general invitations to a platform, where panel members are randomly distributed to ongoing surveys at that moment via a router. Based on known background data, selection questions and set quotas, a panel member is admitted or not admitted to the survey (for this reason, the gross numbers of invited panellists are unknown to the samples from Italy and Sweden).

To prevent respondents from skipping questions or filling in impossible answers, the following rules were applied: respondents were required to fill in all questions before completing the questionnaire; changing of answers was allowed except the selection questions; routing was applied to skip non-applicable questions to the situation of the respondent; where applicable minimum or maximum values were set; where applicable answers were randomised (e.g. in case of a long list of answers to prevent respondents choosing the upper options more frequently); The questionnaire was extensively tested by two researchers (other than the project leader) with regard to its content and technical feasibility. The data provider offered the opportunity to see the online questionnaire through a trial account before it was sent out. The questionnaire was sent out after the final agreement and revision of the research team.

After the research period was completed, the data were screened and processed. Quality checks took place to ensure the data collected is of high quality. These quality checks included looking at open answers, consistency of the answers, straightlining and completion time. Straightlining is a sequence of statements answered with the same answer option. In case of poor response quality, the results of the specific panel member were removed from the data file. The total number of respondents included in the Netherlands was 501, for Sweden 508 and for Italy 506. The number of respondents that were removed from the sample because they dropped out or response quality was poor, was respectively 71, 75 and 43 for the three countries. The net response rate for the stratified sample in the Netherlands was 40.7%. In all three countries, the samples had a relatively

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lower number of respondents in the age group 18-25, which may be explained by the lower number of young people being responsible for grocery shopping. In the samples from Sweden and Italy, people with lower education levels are slightly underrepresented, most likely because they had less interest in the topic. In the analyses, we explored weighted response rates for these two countries regarding education to see whether the corrected statistics showed a different picture when compared to the actual sample.

Sustainability labels

We include labels in our study to get a more complete picture of the potential transition pathways. Including labels is important because consumers are likely to be relatively familiar with this instrument as compared to others.

To develop the questionnaire, we first determined the most important sustainability labels in each country based on desk research. We included the most visible labels in the supermarket as well as smaller labels that are used on at least a national scale. More regionally used labels or specific niche labels that are, for example, specific to short supply chains that source directly from producer countries, were left out. Labels that used the same underlying sustainability standards were combined (such as European organic standards that are sometimes marketed under different label names). Industry-level standards that are generally not marketed to consumers were left out. This may lead to some cases where, for example, the standards are not used in campaigns to make consumers aware, but are occasionally mentioned on packages (like Global GAP). We made decisions for these to the best of our insights, but often lack specific local market expertise. In the questionnaire, we then asked participants:

- For each label in their country, whether they were *aware* of each of the most important food sustainability labels in their country.
- This was followed by a question about what extent they *used* the labels that they are aware of in purchase decisions (on a 7-point scale). In fast-moving consumer goods categories like food, purchase decisions are often routine, and routines emerge on the basis of satisfaction levels from purchase decisions. Consumers are better able to
- Next, we asked to what extent they also trust the labels that they are aware of (on a 7-point scale).

Results are shown in Tables 5.1-5.3.

Table 5.1. Results on sustainability labels in Sweden (n= 508)

Label	Awareness of label (%)	Level of use, mean (sd)	Level of trust, mean (sd)
<i>Labels used in coffee and cocoa</i>			
KRAV	79.92	5.45 (1.50)	5.04 (1.56)
Fairtrade	72.05	5.18 (1.61)	4.61 (1.57)
EU-lövet / EU Organic / EKO / Ekologiskt	37.01	5.20 (1.55)	4.83 (1.59)
Rainforest Alliance	31.3	5.03 (1.71)	4.64 (1.67)
<i>Labels used in cocoa</i>			
Fair for Life	14.37	5.11 (1.59)	5.39 (1.53)
<i>Labels used in other categories</i>			
MSC / ASC Nordic Swan (Svanen)	47.05	5.43 (1.43)	5.31 (1.40)
Svenskt Sigill	40.94	5.39 (1.51)	5.22 (1.40)
Från Sverige	40.52	5.44 (1.45)	5.18 (1.50)
I am not familiar with any of the labels mentioned above	3.94	/	/

Table 5.2. Results on sustainability labels in Italy (n= 506)

Label	Awareness of label (%)	Level of use, mean (sd)	Level of trust, mean (sd)
Labels used in coffee and cocoa			
Fairtrade	60.08	5.29 (1.45)	4.64 (1.67)
EU Organic (Euroblad, Biologico)	53.16	5.32 (1.51)	5.04 (1.56)
Altromercato (fair trade network using its own standards, sometimes direct-trade agreements with coops)	32.81	5.20 (1.42)	4.61 (1.57)
Rainforest Alliance / UTZ	11.86	5.27 (1.49)	4.83 (1.59)
Labels used in other categories			
DOP / IGP / TSG – EU quality schemes for regional products	50.79	5.67 (1.31)	5.39 (1.53)
EU Ecolabel – low-impact packaging and some food-related products	40.91	5.66 (1.35)	5.31 (1.40)
Friend of the Sea –seafood	21.34	5.62 (1.33)	5.18 (1.50)
ICEA certifications – Italian eco-labels (organic, vegan, RSPO palm oil, regenerative organic)	19.96	5.48 (1.35)	5.22 (1.40)
Demeter / Naturland – biodynamic/advanced organic standards	6.32	5.59 (1.36)	5.40 (1.41)
Not familiar with any of the labels mentioned above	12.25	/	/

Table 5.3. Results on sustainability labels in the Netherlands (n= 501)

Label	Awareness of label (%)	Level of use, mean (sd)	Level of trust, mean (sd)
Labels used in coffee and cocoa			
Fairtrade (Max Havelaar)	90.82	5.18 (1.26)	3.80 (1.82)
Rainforest Alliance	42.91	4.87 (1.29)	3.85 (1.78)
EU-Organic/EKO	31.54	5.14 (1.25)	4.21 (1.87)
Demeter	14.77	5.80 (1.24)	4.62 (1.96)
Fair for Life (niche alternative for Fairtrade)	4.59	5.30 (1.11)	4.09 (1,47)
Labels used in other categories			
Better life/Beter leven (animal welfare in meat, dairy, eggs)	84.23	4.80 (1.32)	4.20 (1.82)
On the Way to PlanetProof (horticultural products and dairy)	44.91	4.44 (1.49)	3.36 (1.77)
Not familiar with any of the labels mentioned above	3.39	/	/

In all three countries, many consumers appear to be aware of only some of the labels (FairTrade scores, for example high in all three countries). Some of the labels that have been on the market for a relatively long time are not known to consumers. Less than half of the samples in all three countries, for example, know Rainforest Alliance (in Italy, not even 12 per cent). One limitation here is that we showed only the names of the labels and not the logos, meaning that respondents really had to memorise the names of the labels. Nevertheless, if such labels should be the basis of a transition pathway, consumers should be aware of them, know what they stand for, trust them, and deliberately use them in their purchase decisions. Notably, the labels that most people are aware of, are not the ones that are trusted best. The trust scores for FairTrade are, for example, lower than

for many of the more local labels or labels that target niche markets of engaged consumers (like Demeter). One explanation is that because consumers know these labels that they are also more aware of possible problems in securing their standards. Lower levels of trust do, for example, not necessarily mean lower degrees of usage. Some exceptions to these findings may be national labels that are positioned on issues important in the respective countries. These include Beter Level (animal welfare, responding to problems with intensive animal farming) in the Netherlands, labels related to national origin like Krav in Sweden, and local origin protection and other labels associated with food quality in Italy. Differences in absolute scores between countries should be taken with care, as the use of scales can be influenced by culture.

For telecoupled value chains, the results show the limitations of a labelling pathway. While the majority of consumers are aware of Fairtrade and also the use of that label, their trust in the label is limited. Many consumers don't know the other labels applicable to coffee and cocoa (but if they know them, they are not used less than other labels). In terms of change pathways, it seems logical that labels alone, in their current form, will not bring major changes. Hence, we also look at other instruments.

Instruments other than labels

Consumers may also use other instruments to help them in sustainable decision-making. We asked for several decision-support tools and to what extent they make use of them (using 7-point scales, varying from 1 = "don't use at all", 7 = use a lot). Results are shown in Table 5.4.

Table 5.4: Results on instruments other than labels

	Mean (sd)			
	Sweden (n = 508)	Italy (n = 506)	The Netherlands (n = 501)	Total (N=1515)
Price discounts for sustainable products	4.85 (1.62)	4.79 (1.54)	4.41 (1.68)	4.68 (1,63)
Sustainable products that are placed so that they are easy to find or grab	4.55 (1.70)	4.70 (1.54)	3.63 (1.66)	4.30 (1,70)
Markers in the store that point you at sustainable products	4.50 (1.68)	4.60 (1.60)	3.45 (1.67)	4.19 (1,73)
Campaigns about sustainability aspects of food	4.48 (1.64)	4.43 (1.56)	3.41 (1.59)	4.11 (1,67)
Information from campaigns that publicly question the sustainability of brands	4.21 (1.75)	4.42 (1.65)	3.49 (1.73)	4.04 (1,76)
Advertisements for brands and companies about their sustainability	4.21 (1.76)	4.52 (1.61)	2.98 (1.58)	3.91 (1,78)
Go to specific stores or restaurants that only, or mostly, sell sustainable products, for example Organic stores	3.93 (1.88)	4.36 (1.79)	3.02 (1.85)	3.78 (1,92)
Websites and apps that rank brands and companies based on sustainability	3.94 (1.80)	4.23 (1.71)	2.90 (1.68)	3.69 (1,82)
Apps that make suggestions for healthy or sustainable products for your shopping list	3.94 (1.95)	4.15 (1.78)	2.94 (1.71)	3.68 (1,89)

Most striking insights from the Table above are that price discounts are the most used instrument in all three countries. Price discounts are known to be an effective marketing instrument to

stimulate short-term sales (but not necessarily long-term adoption and behavioural change) (cf. Bijmolt et al. 2005). Also consistent across the three countries is that nudging (sustainable products that are placed so that they are easy to find or grab) is the second highest, directly followed by markers in the store environment, suggesting that consumers recognise themselves being influenced by such actions. Basically, these findings suggest that in consumers' own experience, marketing actions stimulating impulse buying and on-the-spot decision-making are more effective in making them consider buying sustainable products than instruments trying to change their attitudes or increase their awareness, like campaigns and websites. We can of course not rule out that such awareness and attitude instruments are necessary in the first place to make marketing instruments effective in the first place, but it does show that transition pathways purely based on conscious buying behaviour are unlikely and that other, maybe familiarity biases, influence consumers' preferences.

Other than that, the differences between all instruments are relatively small. This is remarkable to the extent that respondents also indicate that they use websites and apps. To some extent, these scores may be influenced by consumer segments that care a lot about being fully informed about their food choices and/or are into new technology and gadgets. In addition, some level of measurement bias may have slipped in because all these instruments were presented directly underneath each other in the questionnaire (through in randomised order). Finally, the results show some differences between the national environments. In Sweden, consumers express, for example, that they are influenced by campaigns, while in the Netherlands, the score for "shaming" is relatively higher.

Consumers' evaluations of hypothetical new products

Based on the final mapping presented in the previous chapter, we also selected four novel ideas that we described in the questionnaire as new product or service interventions. We then asked respondents to provide an overall evaluation ranging from 1 = very bad to 7 = very good. The descriptions of the products and the results are shown in Table 5.5 below.

Table 5.5: Evaluation ratings for product and service descriptions

Product/service description	Mean (sd)			
	Sweden (n = 508)	Italy (n = 506)	The Netherlands (n = 501)	Total (n = 1515)
Subscription to sustainable chocolate directly from Africa You will receive regularly new chocolate, send to you by a courier. You pay an amount every month for a basic package of chocolate, but you can increase by ordering on a website where you can select your flavors, quantities, and frequency. The cocoa for your chocolate will be produced by farmer cooperatives in Africa directly associated with the initiative. The farmers will receive a price above the market price.	4.44 (1.72)	4.59 (1.48)	4.34 (1.57)	4.46 (1.60)
Feedback system telling you the impact of your choices Imagine you can download an app that keeps track of what you order and purchase. The app gives you regularly an assessment of your personal impact on issues such as health, biodiversity, greenhouse gas emissions, animal welfare, and	4.62 (1.62)	4.89 (1.49)	4.13 (1.70)	4.55 (1.63)

fair incomes for farmers around the world. It will also give you suggestions on how you can improve further.				
A pre-selection app Imagine you can download an app that functions as a filter. At one point in time you enter your preferences regarding healthiness of products, possibly allergies, your favorite brands, and your sustainability preferences. You can update this from time to time. The app will give you suggestions on where to shop, when you shop online you can use it as a filter by searching for the products that likely meet your preferences, and it will alert you when your favorite products are on discount.	4.53 (1.60)	4.84 (1.47)	3.98 (1.60)	4.46 (1.60)
The brand that explicitly says NO to sustainability, keeps it cheap for you! Imagine there's a new food brand that explicitly advertises as the brand that "doesn't care about sustainability". Though it sticks to food safety and other laws, it always seeks the cheapest ingredients regardless of the environmental and social consequences. The brand manager argues: "We care about social responsibility, for us social responsibility means that people can eat tasty food at any income level. If you want to save the planet, there are plenty other products that you can buy."	3.98 (1.77)	4.09 (1.75)	3.27 (1.78)	3.78 (1.80)

While the differences between the products/services and the countries are not strikingly big, they do show remarkable differences. The subscription for sustainable chocolate directly from Africa, receives the highest average score in the Netherlands. This is interesting because this innovation pulls consumers explicitly and entirely out of the supermarket system that can be so influential in shaping their decisions. The next two innovations (pre-selection and feedback systems) intend to empower consumers in their current shopping environments to stay closer to their own decisions. While in the Netherlands, these scores are lower than the subscription service, they do score higher than that service in Sweden and Italy. In these countries, the feedback system comes out strongest. From a systems thinking perspective, the problem with a telecoupled value chain is that price signals from price-sensitive consumers ripple down the chain, encouraging all actors to be more cost-efficient, while signals that equity and biodiversity are under pressure at the production level do not ripple back from the producer to the consumer. The suggested feedback system intends to repair exactly this flaw in a telecoupled value chain.

The fourth innovation may be seen as an "anti-sustainability" brand that intends to motivate selfishness and resistance to climate change measures and the like. The results may be influenced by the fact that respondents are in a questionnaire in which they should answer many questions about sustainable purchases (to which they explicitly said yes to begin with). Still, the relatively lower scores on average for this innovation can be seen as an encouragement that consumers in all three countries are not opposing transition pathways towards greater sustainability in the first place.

Consumer efficacy and cultural aspects

We further asked consumers questions on psychological or attitudinal aspects relevant for sustainable decision-making and how they are likely to see policy changes regarding sustainable consumption (all using 7-point Likert scales). A complete list of these items can be found in Annex 2.

First, we included a scale on **ethically minded consumer behaviour**, the extent to which consumers integrate ethical considerations into their consumption choices, including issues such as the environment, animal welfare, fair trade, and working conditions (Sudbury-Riley and Kohlbacher 2016) (10 items, Alpha = 0.84). This scale provides insight into the general attitude to ethical/sustainable consumption.

Next, we asked questions pertaining to **Consumer self-efficacy for sustainable consumption**, which is the extent to which consumers' belief in their ability to make a difference through their own consumption choices (Antonetti and Maklan 2014) (4 items, Alpha = 0.62). The scale offers insight into the extent to which consumers see themselves as capable of shopping in a sustainable manner.

Third, we include items on **Perceived consumer effectiveness**, the extent to which individuals believe that their personal efforts can make a difference in the solution to environmental problems (Ellen, Webb, and Mohr 1991) (5 items, Alpha = 0.80). As such, the scale will give insight into the extent to which consumers feel that sustainable decisions actually matter to solve sustainability problems.

Fourth, we include two scales regarding autonomy, namely **Autonomy satisfaction** (3 items, Alpha = 0.84) and **autonomy frustration** (3 items, Alpha = 0.85) (Chen, et al., 2015). These concepts stem from self-determination theory and refer respectively to the experience of volition and psychological freedom, feeling that one's behavior is self-endorsed and reflects one's authentic interests and values (autonomy satisfaction), and the experience of pressure and control, feeling forced to behave in ways that conflict with one's authentic preferences, and experiencing one's actions as externally driven rather than self-chosen (autonomy frustration). These are psychological concepts, culturally embedded, that give insight into consumers' attitudes towards more constraining options to increase sustainable consumption.

The means, standard deviations of, and correlations between these constructs are reported in Table 5.6.

Table 5.6: Properties of multi-item measures

		Mean	Sd	Correlations (Pearson)*			
				(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
(1)	Ethically minded consumer behaviour	4.19	1.01	1			
(2)	Self-efficacy for sustainable consumption	4.22	1.03	0.49	1		
(3)	Perceived consumer effectiveness	4.01	0.05	0.16	0.33	1	
(4)	Autonomy satisfaction	3.78	1.52	0.47	0.37	0.15	1
(5)	Autonomy frustration	3.84	1.56	0.43	0.35	0.12	0.77

- All correlations are significant at $p < .0001$

The average scores for autonomy are lower than those for the other constructs which show that overall, consumers are moderately ethically minded, feel able to make their own choices (self-efficacy), and are neither positive nor negative that consumers can make difference. The score for ethically minded consumer behaviour of 4.19 suggests that consumers in our sample on average are not extremely high or low when it comes to sustainable consumption. On average they take a middle position and with an average spread of 1.01 the average differences within the sample are not too big. This is important for the interpretation of our results as the sample is not "self-selected" leading to overrepresentation of typically "green" consumers or consumers that object sustainable consumption. The standard deviation for perceived consumer effectiveness is very low (.05), which means that many respondents agree that consumers are neither effective nor ineffective as change-makers. We inspected the data for the different countries, but these didn't show important deviations from the general picture.

Interestingly, autonomy satisfaction and frustration are positively correlated, suggesting that people feel satisfied and frustrated with their freedom in making food choices at the same time. A logical explanation is that on the one hand, consumers are used to the system in which they do their food shoppings and can apply their routine purchases, leading to satisfaction. On the other hand, they may feel that that same system is frustrating them, as they sometimes may feel a ball played by big brands, supermarkets, webshops and the like, which they may perceive as a loss of autonomy leading to frustration. This is a finding with far-reaching implications, as it portrays food shoppers as a bird in a cage: on the one hand longing for freedom, on the other hand attached to the security and habit of what is known. When changing the system to reduce frustration and empower consumers' agency may at the same time lead to decreased satisfaction. Given this paradox, which policies do consumers prefer to set changes in motion?

6. Co-development of transformative change pathways

The broadened perspective presented from the mapping spurs discussion on new directions. The debate, thus far, has perhaps been unbalanced in that much attention goes to existing instruments, like sustainability labels, while other instruments have been neglected and less used. We know very little about the pathways that consumers prefer (see as conclusion in Chapter 5). This is something that we will address in the first experimental study presented in this chapter.

Discrete choice experiment

To determine consumers' preferences for the different options, we designed a choice experiment in which each of the eleven options is a profile. The aim is to obtain a preference-based ranking of these different profiles, something that can be created with a choice experiment. The eleven profiles were briefly formulated in a language understandable for respondents and in a way that they sound like deviations from the current state. The current situation was added as a twelfth profile representing a status quo in which nothing changes. This allows us in the analyses to compute the coefficients as part of the logistic regression as relative deviations from the status quo (The no change variable), predicting the respondents' preferred options in comparison to the "No change" category. The list of pairs of options is included in Annex 3.

We used the same three-country sample as described in the previous chapter. We designed sets of profile comparisons in R and checked the outcomes manually to ensure that all pairs related to others equally. All profile options were included twice; to minimize chances of anchoring bias they appeared once on the left- and once on the right-hand side. The pairs were presented to respondents in random order. After the twelve pairs, respondents saw two more pairs as hold-out questions, and they received two attention checks. The attention checks included two questions that logically had only one correct answer, to check whether respondents had paid attention during the main task.

We analyzed the data with the statistical software of data science (STATA ver16) (<https://www.stata.com/>). To check whether participants had completed the questionnaire carefully, an attention check question was used. The results show that 72% of participants answered the question correctly by selecting the correct 'sustainability rankings', while 27.66% selected the 'no change' option. Although these questions cannot be considered a guarantee of participants' attention, they do provide a good indication that the vast majority completed the questionnaire carefully (e.g., Kung et al., 2018).

Following the logistics regression analysis, to estimate the probability of the binary decision for or against the choice of the options presented, we model the respondents preferences for or against an options in comparison to the status quo, being no change in the system, using a logistic function to ensure predicted values remain between 0 and 1.

The results of the logistic regression, including all respondents from the three countries, are displayed in Table 6.1.

Table 6.1. Ranking of the profiles from the choice experiment based on the coefficients from the Logit regression test and the Post-hoc test of Marginal effects.

Rank	Policy alternative	Coefficient log regression. Total sample**	Value of the coefficient of the Marginal effects post hoc test. Total sample **
1	Price decreases and increases	2.66	0.93
2	Sustainability labels and reminders	2.31	0.91
3	Sustainability rankings	2.29	0.91
4	Loyalty points	1.64	0.84
5	Education campaigns	1.57	0.83
6	Every store one sustainability level	1.39	0.80
7	Unintended purchases	1.01	0.73
8	Pre-selected products	0.95	0.72
9	Legislative ban on unsustainable products	0.84	0.70
10	Licensing	0.69	0.67
11	Naming & Shaming	0.19	0.55
11	No change	/	0.51

**The test is statistically significant with 99% of confidence ($p \leq 0.001$) for all the variables.

The general results over all three countries show that reducing price differences between sustainable and unsustainable products has the highest chance in odds to be selected in comparison to the “no change” option. This is not surprising given that price is one of the dominant factors in consumer (sustainable) decision-making (cf. Bijmolt et al. 2005), being a familiar intervention to drive behavior change. Other preferred options are placing more emphasis on labels and pointing them out more clearly in the store environment, sustainability rankings, loyalty points for the purchase of sustainable products for nice extras. Notably, these are all changes that can be made within the store environment.

Also interesting are the lower effects of “legal bans”, “licensing”, “unintended purchases” and “preselection”, which may indicate a disliking of (perceived) reduced choice of freedom. We write “perceived” because only in the cases of licensing and legal bans, choice of freedom is reduced. In the case of unintended purchases, psychological tools are used to “trick” consumers into sustainable purchases they did not intend to make. In the case of pre-selected products, the constraints are based on their own choices (remarkably, when we presented this idea as a new service app in Chapter 5, the evaluation seemed moderately positive. The results here seem to indicate that consumers perceive this app as reducing their choice of freedom.

The low score of shaming is also remarkable, given that this strategy is popular among action groups to inform consumers. The distinction between shaming on the one hand and sustainability rankings is also sharp. Sustainability rankings also indicate the differences between brands or products but do so more objectively without the interpretation and public debate. The message from consumers seems clear: “just give us the information, present it in a clear and supporting way so that we can make our own decisions, and stop making noise and trying to constrain us.”

Figure 6.1 Probability of choice of the different alternative variables for the whole sample (N=1512) with 99% of confidence. (Marginal effects coefficients calculations + - the standard deviation)

Table 6.2. Values of the post hoc test of Marginal effects for the different countries

Policy alternative	Sweden**	Italy**	The Netherlands**
Price decreases and increases	0.90	0.94	0.96
Sustainable labels and reminders	0.88	0.90	0.94
Sustainable rankings	0.91	0.89	0.93
Loyalty points	0.85	0.80	0.86
Education campaigns	0.81	0.84	0.83
Unintended purchases	0.75	0.66	0.77
Every store one sustainability level	0.83	0.86	0.70
Pre-selected products	0.72	0.79	0.66
Legislative ban on unsustainable products	0.76	0.71	0.63
Licensing	0.67	0.71	0.61
No change	0.60	0.47	0.58
Naming & Shaming	0.56	0.59	0.39

**The test is statistically significant with 99% of confidence ($p \leq 0.001$) for all the variables.

Figure 6.2. Probability of choice of the different alternative variables for the three countries, with 99% of confidence. (Marginal effects coefficient calculations)

The results of the marginal values test per country further show the same tendency as the general results, where the probability of a consumer for choosing one of the policy options is higher for the category of “Price decrease and increases”, and where the probability is lower for consumers to choose “No choice” and “Shaming”. Some interesting differences emerge. The option of every store one sustainability level is welcomed as a good idea in both Italy (ranked number 4) and Sweden (ranked number 5), but not so much in the Netherlands. Respondents in Italy find the option of stimulating unintended purchases of sustainable products, a bad idea (just above making no changes). A possible explanation is that consumers in Italy are more conscious about food purchases anyway, thus finding stimulating unconscious food choices a bad idea. The Swedish respondents are relatively more positive about a legal ban than in the other two countries, though the option still appears in the bottom half.

We further asked respondents to rate all the 11 options in terms of (1) the extent to which they find that the option constrains them in their choice of freedom (Table 6.3), and (2) the likelihood that the option will make a positive difference for sustainability (Table 6.4).

For analyzing the freedom of choice, we asked the participants to provide an overall evaluation to what extent the different policy options constrain their freedom as a consumer, ranging from 1 = not at all constrained to 7 = very not much constrained. The results are stated in the Table 6.3 below.

Table 6.3. Extent that policy options limit the freedom of choice of European Consumers

Ranking	Policy alternative	Mean (sd)			Total (N=1515)
		Sweden (n = 508)	Italy (n = 506)	The Netherlands (n = 501)	

1	Legislative ban on unsustainable products	4.40 (1.73)	4.34 (1.65)	4.95 (1.81)	4.56 (1.75)
2	Licensing	4.40 (1.64)	4.32 (1.45)	4.62 (1.84)	4.44 (1.66)
3	Price decreases and increases	4.02 (1.74)	4.42 (1.59)	3.58 (1.81)	4.01 (1.75)
4	Naming & shaming	4.19 (1.78)	4.30 (1.43)	3.30 (1.94)	3.93 (1.79)
5	Every store one sustainability level	4.00 (1.72)	4.26 (1.42)	3.43 (1.80)	3.90 (1.69)
6	Pre-selected products	4.11 (1.64)	4.35 (1.42)	3.16 (1.75)	3.88 (1.68)
7	Loyalty points	3.94 (1.75)	4.30 (1.48)	2.88 (1.59)	3.71 (1.72)
8	Unintended purchases	3.96 (1.65)	4.29 (1.42)	2.87 (1.63)	3.71 (1.69)
9	Sustainable labels and reminders	3.89 (1.72)	4.35 (1.45)	2.77 (1.67)	3.67 (1.75)
10	Sustainable rankings	3.80 (1.68)	4.42 (1.45)	2.67 (1.59)	3.64 (1.73)
11	Education campaigns	3.79 (1.72)	4.41 (1.46)	2.51 (1.61)	3.57 (1.78)

Roughly, the results are consistent with the theoretical ranking provided in Table 4.2. At the extremes, the results are identical: legislative bans and licensing are associated with least freedom, while education campaigns are followed by sustainability rankings are associated with most freedom. Shaming is perceived as much more restrictive than theoretically expected. While, in theory, we categorized it as an information instrument, consumers seem to perceive it as more restrictive, perhaps because the information doesn't come from a "neutral" source like the Government, but from NGOs that have their own agendas. The instrument of providing every store with a fixed sustainability level is seen as less restrictive than expected. Consumers may see it more as an instrument that aids their choices than that steers it. Pre-selecting products they see instead more at the level of steering instruments than aiding instruments.

Following, we also asked participants the extent they think that the different policy options will improve sustainability, ranging from 1 = will not improve sustainability at all to 7 = will improve sustainability a whole lot. The results of the policy alternatives that consumers consider could make a difference in terms of sustainability are presented in Table 6.4 below.

Table 6.4. Policy options that European Consumers suggest that make a difference in sustainability

Ranking	Policy alternative	Mean (sd)			
		Sweden (n = 508)	Italy (n = 506)	The Netherlands (n = 501)	Total (N=1515)
1	Price decreases and increases	5.02 (1.53)	4.92 (1.51)	5.02 (1.48)	5.02 (1.53)
2	Legislative ban on unsustainable products	4.80 (1.69)	4.67 (1.65)	4.67 (0.02)	4.80 (1.69)
3	Sustainability labels and reminders	4.60 (1.43)	4.66 (1.53)	4.92 (1.30)	4.69 (1.41)
4	Loyalty points	4.67 (1.47)	4.83 (1.49)	4.85 (1.41)	4.67 (1.47)
5	Education campaigns	4.65 (1.43)	4.79 (0.14)	4.90 (1.39)	4.65 (1.43)
6	Sustainability rankings	4.69 (1.41)	4.78 (1.43)	4.90 (1.35)	4.60 (1.43)
7	Unintended purchases	4.53 (1.41)	4.63 (1.46)	4.73 (1.34)	4.53 (1.41)
8	Licensing	4.50 (1.55)	4.45 (1.60)	4.60 (1.41)	4.50 (1.55)
9	Every store one sustainability level	4.43 (1.49)	4.56 (1.53)	4.80 (1.32)	4.43 (1.49)
10	Pre-selected products	4.38 (1.44)	4.36 (1.53)	4.72 (1.35)	4.38 (1.44)
11	Naming and Shaming	4.14 (1.63)	4.04 (1.73)	4.61 (1.43)	4.14 (1.63)

The results here are remarkable in that consumers expect that the price instrument will be even more impactful for sustainability than legislative bans. Also sustainability rankings and the use of loyalty points are remarkably high given the relatively limited use of these instruments in practice and their relatively small role in academic and public debates.

VR experiment on technology-driven decision-aid tools

Introduction and background

As prices have been identified as prominent drivers for consumer behavior change towards greater sustainability, a small follow-up experiment was conducted to test whether technology-driven decision support systems can help consumers in their sustainable shopping decisions. More precisely the second experimental study explored how a **decision aid**—a data-driven filtering system embedded in a virtual-reality (VR) supermarket—might help consumers make more sustainable choices by reducing their price sensitivity. The study investigated whether a personalized, technology-supported decision aid could harmonise egoistic motives (seeking affordability and self-benefit) with collective motives (caring for the environment and society) (Ingenbleek, Meulenberg & van Trijp, 2015), thereby encouraging more sustainable purchase decisions.

The decision aid was designed to enhance motivation and ability (MacInnis et al., 1991) by allowing users to indicate which sustainability attributes they valued most—such as local origin, organic production, sustainable packaging, or animal welfare—after which only the recommended product fitting their choice was displayed. By blurring out other options and, particularly, prices, the system sought to simplify decision-making and redirect attention away from cost towards self-relevant sustainability benefits.

Methods

The experimental study was conducted in an immersive VR supermarket in the consumer lab at Wageningen University. Each participant completed two shopping sessions: one in a control condition, where all products and prices were visible, and one in an experimental condition, where the decision aid displayed a single recommended sustainable product while all other products were blurred. The VR supermarket was created in Unity Game engine (<https://unity.com>) and viewed through a Varjo XR-3 headset with hand controllers, providing a realistic yet controllable simulation of a shopping experience. Participants (N = 29; 10 male, 19 female; average age 23) were recruited from Wageningen University and Research. While the sample size was small, this was justified by the exploratory and experimental nature of the study. In VR-based experiments, smaller samples are common due to setup complexity and time intensity, and, aligned with the study 1 results, the goal was to generate early behavioral insights rather than broad statistical generalization.

Participants were instructed to imagine buying ingredients for a pasta Bolognese meal for four people, using their normal grocery budget. They shopped twice—once in the control setting and once with the decision aid. After each condition, they filled in a questionnaire measuring perceived self-appeal of products, level of trust in the system, involvement in using it, experienced conflict between self-interest and collective benefit, and sensitivity to price. Statistical analyses were conducted using non-parametric tests, as the data did not meet assumptions of normality. Mediation and moderation analyses were performed using bootstrapped estimates to account for the small sample size and non-normal distribution.

Results

The results were surprising, indicating that the decision aid tool did not confirm the expectation that the decision aid would reduce consumers' price sensitivity. On the contrary, participants were slightly more price-sensitive in the decision-aid condition than in the control condition. This suggests that restricting visible product options may have increased consumers' awareness of prices rather than diminishing it, shifting the focus of attention. The sustainable products presented

through the decision aid were not perceived as significantly more appealing to the self than those in the unrestricted setting, although a small trend toward significance indicated that this effect could emerge more strongly in a larger sample sizes.

Discussion

These outcomes highlight the psychological complexity of guiding consumers towards sustainability through technological interventions. Rather than harmonizing self-interest and collective motives, the decision aid may have reduced consumers' sense of autonomy (freedom of choice) by removing choice options. Many participants expressed frustration at not being able to choose freely, suggesting that the restriction itself triggered resistance. This response aligns with theories of psychological reactance, which propose that individuals resist when they feel their freedom of choice is threatened. Losing the ability to compare options might have made participants feel less ownership over their decisions, increasing skepticism and attention to price. More importantly, however, the results are in line with the findings of this report, clearly indicating the consumers' freedom of choice as a driving element for telecoupled sustainability products and goods, while also preferring existing governance interventions. However, participants also saw the potential benefits of the decision aid tool. Several consumers indicated that the idea of a technology-driven decision aid system for ecolabels was appealing, as it could simplify shopping in supermarkets crowded with confusing sustainability claims. They appreciated that the decision aid could make sustainable shopping less effortful, even if the current implementation felt too restrictive. The mixed responses suggest that consumers value guidance but still want to retain control.

7. Pathways, conclusions, and implications

In this report we take a consumer perspective to provide a state-of-the-art mapping of instruments and develop new pathways to transform telecoupled value chains to greater levels of equity, biodiversity and other sustainability aspects. In the state-of-the-art mapping, we developed eleven different instruments and included them as different options. We did not place more emphasis on options that receive more attention in public and/or academic debates but rather tried to be complete and comprehensive. Our results show that in all three countries, consumers do have a desire for change: Of all the options they were confronted with “no change” often ranked as one of the lowest.

The current debate focuses mostly on sustainability labels. When seeing a lack of sustainability that emerges in a telecoupled value chain as a form of market failure, likely caused by information asymmetry, sustainability labels are a logical pathway: they inform consumers about externalities and consumers can take that information on board when making decisions. Assuming that consumers are rational beings that care about the future of humans and the planet on which they live, the likely outcome is that consumers massively chose products with sustainability labels. Unfortunately, the reality of consumer decision-making is far more complex and psychologically biased (cf. Ingenbleek & Krampe, 2022). The results in our report again confirmed that while labels are well-established, consumers are not by definition aware of them, and their indicated level of use in purchase decisions is moderate.

Hence, our mapping serves a purpose by taking a broader perspective by including different instruments. The mapping isn't just broader, it also takes a different perspective, namely choice freedom. The instruments could be placed in categories that inform, aid, steer, or even restrict their decisions. With a few exceptions, the consumers in our sample place them in a comparable order.

Our results are remarkable in that they deviate from the traditional emphasis on labels and draw attention to other instruments by decreasing the price difference between sustainable and non-sustainable products to number one in all three countries. The same consumers placed this instrument relatively high in their ranking of instruments that constrain their choice freedom. This finding may suggest that the respondents did not interpret this instrument as “a free sustainable lunch” in which the government heavily subsidizes their sustainable purchases. The finding can be seen as that consumers are aware that it comes at the burden of paying more for everything that is

not sustainable. In the same line as the price instrument also the instrument loyalty points received relatively high scores. Again, remarkable because the instrument is hardly part of the debate and, like price changes, points at the mechanisms of rewarding sustainable behavior.

Another instrument that scored relatively high was sustainability rankings. Again, remarkable because such rankings already exist: they are available through websites and apps and are used by NGOs in shaming campaigns. The latter are in fact disliked by consumers. This is again a remarkable finding because such campaigns are part of our current public debate. When asked to what extent consumers use apps and websites, they appear almost at the bottom of the list. This suggests that these rankings are currently underutilized. Rather than being put away in an app or on a website, they can, for example, be communicated directly in the shopping environment or even be used to organize the shelves. Comparably with the emphasis on prices and other rewards, the results may tell: Why does the shopping environment make it so difficult for consumers to make sustainable choices?

The store environment seems very much guiding consumers in their choices as the top of the list of what they are using in their decisions are all instruments that relate to the shopping environment: discounts, placement in the store that makes products easy to find, clear markers for sustainable products. At the same time, apps and other instruments that help consumers to cope with the store environment are less used and less desired. The message seems: “why should we use apps on our phone in the store and study rankings before shopping, it is much easier if these things are integrated in the store environment in which we make our decisions.”

The clearest new pathway that comes out of our analyses is therefore to change the store environment with among others clearer information (rankings), price interventions, pointers at sustainable products, and removing distractive adds for unsustainable products. This pathway would leave the freedom to decide with the consumer (consumers seem really attached to that), but it makes the sustainable choice much easier by making the store environment not so much supportive for the profits of the store owner but for sustainability. As such, the pathway will be no doubt find resistance on its way from the store, which is also attached to the free market principle of being the boss in its own store.

Some concrete actions that can be taken to start shaping this pathway: (1) start a public debate on the role of supermarkets and other stores in sustainability transitions. Don't blame consumers for making unsustainable decisions but question the role of those that have a direct influence on these decisions. (2) Create discussion platforms with retailers and representative organizations of retailers to discuss what if-scenarios: a safe environment in which retailers can share the potential consequences before immediately attacking them. Rather call on their responsibility and work together on co-created solutions that may change their revenue models but that will not necessarily destroy their profit potential. (3) Start exploring the legal barriers and opportunities for potential interventions in the price system and store environment, so that when necessary some pressure can be used to create the supportive shopping environment that consumers are asking for. In particular, changing the price system is complex system change as it does not just involve the price levels used in the stores for the prices paid by the consumer, but also the incentives that such prices provide for all the suppliers in the value chains leading to these stores. It is in the chain, in particular at the basis of the chain, where the most important impact can be made for sustainability.

While changing the shopping environment is the clearest pathway suggested by our results, we mention one other pathway, namely strengthening the feedback from sustainability to consumers. This pathway is informed by the highest-ranked of four hypothetical products that we asked consumers to rate. When thinking from the perspective of systems, for example, systems that develop do so on the basis of feedback. In our current food system feedback is mostly one-directional. Consumers' demand is translated in the form of price signals that ripple through the chain, ultimately incentivizing primary producers to intensify production, which can easily go at the expense of biodiversity and equity. Feedback in the other direction is mostly nonexistent: signals on declining biodiversity and poor equity will not reach consumers through the same chain of actors and mechanisms. Price signals from the supply side only transfer through the chain when supply declines, for example due to declining harvests, which can indirectly be caused by environmental degradation or depopulation of the countryside due to among others low prices paid to farmers. Better feedback mechanisms can improve the adaptability of food systems to biodiversity, equity

and other sustainability problems on the supply side. Also, the preferences of the respondents in Italy and Sweden, who found this the most appealing service that we asked them to evaluate, are in that respect exemplary.

Finally, we indicate some limitations and directions for future research. Our study targeted grocery shoppers. This means that the majority of people in our sample are likely to frequent visitors of supermarkets and perhaps other stores, but that it didn't include other consumers within the households. There are many people nowadays that don't do the shopping for groceries, but do order food online or purchase food in HoReCa. This is a limitation of our study that future research can take into account.

More research is needed to examine differences between segments and influences of familiarity effects. Part of consumers' preferences for example lower prices and sustainability labels, may not be explained by the fact that they really want it, but by the fact that they are used to it. The food environment is changing with greater influence of out of home eating, delivery, and new technologies (e-commerce, AI). Future research may examine whether our findings hold in an environment that rules out familiarity with the current food environment, for example by placing the choice experiment in an experimental game setting.

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9. ANNEX 1: Literature reviewed

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10. ANNEX 2: Multi-item-scales in the Consumer questionnaire

Ethically minded consumer behavior (Sudbury-Riley & Kohlbacher 2016)

- When there is a choice, I always choose the product that contributes to the least amount of environmental damage.
- I have switched products for environmental reasons.
- If I understand the potential damage to the environment that some products can cause, I do not purchase those products.
- I do not buy household products that harm the environment.
- Whenever possible, I buy products packaged in reusable or recyclable containers.
- I make every effort to buy paper products (toilet paper, tissues, etc.) made from recycled paper.
- I will not buy a product if I know that the company that sells it is socially irresponsible.
- I do not buy products from companies that I know use sweatshop labor, child labor, or other poor working conditions.
- I have paid more for environmentally friendly products when there is a cheaper alternative.
- I have paid more for socially responsible products when there is a cheaper alternative.

Self-Efficacy for Sustainable Consumption (Antonetti and maklan 2014)

- I feel able to make sustainable consumption choices.
- I believe I have the skills to reduce my environmental impact through my purchases.
- I feel confident in my ability to act in a sustainable way as a consumer.
- I can successfully choose environmentally responsible products when I shop

Perceived consumer effectiveness (adapted from Ellen, Web, and Mohr 1991)

- Each consumer's behavior can have a positive effect on sustainability by purchasing products sold by socially responsible companies.
- Consumers can be effective in influencing sustainability problems.
- It is worthless for the individual consumer to do anything about sustainability. (*reverse-coded*)
- When I buy products, I try to consider how my use of them will affect sustainability and other consumers.
- Since one person cannot have any effect upon sustainability problems, it doesn't make any difference what I do. (*reverse-coded*)

Autonomy Satisfaction (Adapted from Chen et al., 2015)

- I feel a sense of choice and freedom when I make food choices.
- I feel that my food purchase decisions reflect what I really want.
- I feel that my food choices express who I really am.

Autonomy Frustration (Adapted from Chen et al., 2015)

- I feel pressured to do too many things in my food choices.
- I feel forced to do things I wouldn't choose to do when making food choices.
- I feel that my food choices are more controlled than I would like.

11. ANNEX 3: Pairs of profiles used in the Choice Experiment

What would you chose to do more compared to how things are going now?

a.	<p style="text-align: center;">Shaming</p> <p>More “shaming” campaigns that tell consumers which brands and companies are not sustainable, so that consumers may get disappointed in these brands and companies.</p>	OR	<p style="text-align: center;">Sustainability rankings</p> <p>Put more pressure on companies to disclose detailed sustainability information that can be used to rank companies from most to least sustainable.</p>
b.	<p style="text-align: center;">Unintended purchases</p> <p>Make stores position more sustainable products in prominent areas within the store, such as at eye level, to increase the chance that consumers unintentionally chose these products.</p>	OR	<p style="text-align: center;">Pre-selected products</p> <p>Promote apps and other technology tools to help consumers to pre-select products that they find sufficiently sustainable, so that they get less distracted by the unsustainable products in the store.</p>
c.	<p style="text-align: center;">Loyalty points</p> <p>Make stores offer considerably more loyalty points with the purchase of sustainable products and considerably less with unsustainable products.</p>	OR	<p style="text-align: center;">Legislative ban on unsustainable products</p> <p>Remove more unsustainable products entirely from all stores by law.</p>
d.	<p style="text-align: center;">No change</p> <p>Keep things the way they are now, not making any changes.</p>	OR	<p style="text-align: center;">Every store one sustainability level</p> <p>Introduce sustainability labels for stores, so that consumers choose their preferred sustainability level when they decide which store they go. The most sustainable store would for example be an Organic store. In the store the products differ less in sustainability than they do now.</p>
e.	<p style="text-align: center;">Education campaigns</p> <p>More information for consumers about the sustainability impacts of specific products through public awareness campaigns.</p>	OR	<p style="text-align: center;">Loyalty points</p> <p>Make stores offer considerably more loyalty points with the purchase of sustainable products and considerably less with unsustainable products.</p>
f.	<p style="text-align: center;">Sustainability labels and reminders</p> <p>Use more visual signals in the store, such as sustainability labels and highlights, to remind consumers which products are sustainable.</p>	OR	<p style="text-align: center;">Shaming</p> <p>More “shaming” campaigns that tell consumers which brands and companies are not sustainable, so that consumers may get disappointed in these brands and companies.</p>
g.	<p style="text-align: center;">Licensing</p> <p>Introduce licenses for purchasing unsustainable products, so that only users that really need these products, like for example food banks, can purchase them.</p>	OR	<p style="text-align: center;">Price decreases and increases</p> <p>Use tax instruments to make sustainable products cheaper at the expense of unsustainable products that become more expensive.</p>

h.	Legislative ban on unsustainable products	OR	Licensing
	Remove more unsustainable products entirely from all stores by law.		Introduce licenses for purchasing unsustainable products, so that only users that really need these products, like for example food banks, can purchase them.

i.	Every store one sustainability level	OR	Sustainability labels and reminders
	Introduce sustainability labels for stores, so that consumers choose their preferred sustainability level when they decide which store they go. The most sustainable store would for example be an Organic store. In the store the products differ less in sustainability than they do now.		Use more visual signals in the store, such as sustainability labels and highlights, to remind consumers which products are sustainable.

j.	Price decreases and increases	OR	No change
	Use tax instruments to make sustainable products cheaper at the expense of unsustainable products that become more expensive.		Keep things the way they are now, not making any changes.

k.	Pre-select products	OR	Education campaigns
	Promote apps and other technology tools to help consumers to pre-select products that they find sufficiently sustainable, so that they get less distracted by the unsustainable products in the store.		More information for consumers about the sustainability impacts of specific products through public awareness campaigns.

l.	Sustainability rankings	OR	Unintended purchases
	Put more pressure on companies to disclose detailed sustainability information that can be used to rank companies from most to least sustainable.		Make stores position more sustainable products in prominent areas within the store, such as at eye level, to increase the chance that consumers unintentionally chose these products.

Holdout questions:

m.	Loyalty points	OR	Every store one sustainability level
	Make stores offer considerably more loyalty points with the purchase of sustainable products and considerably less with unsustainable products.		Introduce sustainability labels for stores, so that consumers choose their preferred sustainability level when they decide which store they go. The most sustainable store would for example be an Organic store. In the store the products differ less in sustainability than they do now.

n.	Sustainability rankings	OR	No change
	Put more pressure on companies to disclose detailed sustainability information that can be used to rank companies from most to least sustainable.		Keep things the way they are now, not making any changes.

Attention checks:

Thank you for your answers so far. On the next page you see two other questions with answers to choose from. Please read these questions also carefully.

Please select the option that is best for sustainability

a.	Legislative ban on unsustainable products	OR	No change
	Remove more unsustainable products entirely from all stores by legislation.		Keep things the way they are now, not making any changes.

Which of the following options was not mentioned earlier in the choices you were asked to make:

b.	Communal food systems	OR	Sustainability rankings
	Producing, distributing, and consuming food that are organized and managed collectively by a community rather than by individual households or large private corporations.		Put more pressure on companies to disclose detailed sustainability information that can be used to rank companies from most to least sustainable.

